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Time Resource Availability And Utilization For The Attainment Of Sustainable Development Goal 4 In Public Secondary Schools In Enugu State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated Time Resource Availability and Utilization for the Attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in Public Secondary Schools in Enugu State. The study was guided by 2 objectives, 2 research questions and 1 hypothesis. A descriptive survey design was adopted. The population comprised 293 principals of all public secondary schools in Enugu States and all 8594 teachers, giving a total population of 8887 male and female. The sample size of 379 respondents, was drawn using the stratified sampling technique. A questionnaire titled Resource Availability and Utilization for the Attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 Questionnaire (RAUASDGQ) and a 5-item checklist were used to gather data. The instruments were validated by the researcher's supervisor and two other experts at the University of Port Harcourt. Research Question 1 was done using a checklist while research question 2 was scored using a modified 4 Likert Scale of Very Great Extent (VGE) =4, Great Extent (GE) =3, Less Extent (LE) =2, and Very Low Extent (VLE) =1. Cronbach's Alpha was used to determine the reliability of the study. The reliability index of 0.85 was ascertained which was considered reliable and adequate for the study. Research question 1 raised in the study was answered using Percentage, while research question 2 raised in the study was answered using Mean and Standard Deviation, while z-test statistics were used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significant. The findings revealed that adequate time resources are available towards the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Based on the findings, it was concluded that, time resources are available in public secondary schools in Enugu State. It was recommended among others that there is a great need to increase the efficiency of educational resource management in other to enable all basic educational institutions to carry out their functions more efficiently and effectively.

Keyword: Time Resource, Availability, Utilization, Sustainable Development Goal 4, Public Secondary Schools, Enugu State.

INTRODUCTION

In today's fast-paced world, access to quality educational resources is crucial for students, educators, and society. These resources' availability and effective utilization significantly shape the learning experiences and foster academic success. The availability and efficient use of resources in public secondary schools are paramount to achieving Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), which aims to guarantee inclusive and equitable quality education and encourage opportunities for lifelong learning for everyone. In particular, the relationship between resource availability, usage, and SDG 4 achievement is intricate and crucial in Enugu State. Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), which aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all, remains a critical component of global development efforts. For Nigeria, and particularly for

Enugu State, achieving this goal requires addressing various resource constraints within the public secondary education system. Among these resources, time plays a pivotal role, influencing both teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes. However, the availability and efficient utilization of time as a resource within the school system are often underexamined in the context of SDG 4 attainment.

Every school activity is allocated some time frame within which the activities are to be accomplished. Within the school, there is time for morning assembly, time for lessons, break time, holidays, etc. School goals will not be achieved and every effort by the human resources will be futile when time is not effectively utilized. Human resources make use of time when performing functions. Time is utilized to maintain facilities, delegate functions, or even spend fiscal cash. More so, the effective and efficient utilization of time brings about achievement of high quality education. In public secondary schools, the management of time is essential for ensuring that curricula are adequately covered, extracurricular activities are balanced, and opportunities for students to engage in meaningful learning are maximized. In this regard, effective time allocation and utilization are critical to optimizing teaching practices, student engagement, and administrative efficiency. Time-related challenges, such as teacher absenteeism, student absenteeism, poorly planned school timetables, and interruptions to academic schedules due to socio-political factors, often hamper the quality of education delivered in public schools. These challenges may lead to gaps in learning, inadequate preparation for national examinations, and overall poor academic performance, hindering the state's efforts to meet SDG 4. Understanding the extent to which time is available and how it is utilized could reveal critical insights into improving teaching methodologies, increasing instructional time, and enhancing the overall learning environment. By addressing the issue of time resource management, public secondary schools in Enugu can better align with SDG 4, contributing to the broader goal of transforming education systems to foster sustainable development across Nigeria.

Sustainable Development Goals: As Wikipedia (2023) puts it, in 2015, 193 countries of the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) created the Sustainable Development Goals as part of the post-2015 Development Agenda. This agenda sought to design a new global development framework, replacing the Millennium Development Goals, which were completed that same year. These goals were formally articulated and adopted in the UNGA resolution known as the 2030 Agenda. On 6th July 2017, the SDGs were made more actionable by a UNGA resolution that identifies specific targets for each goal and provides indicators to measure progress. As Wikipedia further explained the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) or Global Goals are a collection of seventeen (17) interlinked objectives designed to serve as a shared blueprint for peace and prosperity for people and the planet, now and into the future. This international policy framework provides a road map to end poverty, provide healthcare, provide inclusive and equitable quality education and long-life learning opportunities for all, and prosperity for all while protecting the planet. The 2030 agenda for SDG represents a common framework of international cooperation to promote sustainable development.

Availability refers to the existence of an item within a particular environment where it is needed. The concept of availability generally refers to the state of something being present and accessible or the extent to which something is readily available or obtainable when needed or desired. It implies that a particular item, resource, service, or opportunity is easily accessible or within reach (Audu, 2021). Availability can pertain to various aspects of life, including the availability of goods, services, resources, information, opportunities, or even personal time. Utilization refers to the act or process of making use of something effectively or efficiently. Market Business News (2023) had it that, utilization is the act of putting something to use, i.e., using it in a useful and efficient way. Simply put, the phrase relates to using something or the act of doing so in an efficient manner. Utilization in business can also mean the proportion of time that a machine, gadget, or staff is actively working. The phrase can also refer to a brief period of a system's operational time. To achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in secondary schools, resources must be used effectively and efficiently to meet the goals of the SDGs at the institutional level. To advance excellent education, guarantee inclusivity, promote sustainable practices, and improve general well-being within the school community, realistic management of financial, human, infrastructural, and pedagogical resources must be implemented.

Statement of the Problem

The attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) in public secondary schools in Enugu State is challenged by the availability and utilization of time resources. SDG 4 aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. However, achieving this goal requires not only financial and physical resources but also effective time management in school systems. Public secondary schools in Enugu State face time-related constraints such as insufficient instructional hours, overcrowded timetables, and ineffective utilization of available time. These issues hinder the implementation of quality educational programs, the full coverage of curricula, and the provision of individualized attention to students. Teachers are often burdened with administrative tasks, limiting their classroom teaching time, while students struggle with packed schedules that offer little room for extracurricular and developmental activities. Furthermore, a lack of coordination in time resource management reduces the effectiveness of learning outcomes, posing a significant threat to the realization of SDG 4 targets. This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the availability and utilization of time resources in public secondary schools in Enugu State and its implications for achieving SDG 4.

Aim and objectives of the study

This study aimed to investigate time resource availability and utilization for the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) in public secondary schools in Enugu State, Nigeria. In particular, this study sought to:

7. access the availability of time resources to ensure productivity and the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in public secondary schools in Enugu State.
8. investigate the utilization of time resources for the attainment of productivity and Sustainable Development Goal 4 in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Research questions

5. What is the availability of time resources in public secondary schools in Enugu State to ensure productivity and the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4?
6. To what extent are time Resources adequately allocated in Public Secondary Schools in Enugu State for the attainment of productivity and Sustainable Development Goal 4?

Hypothesis

3. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male teachers and female teachers regarding the extent to which time Resources are adequately allocated in Public Secondary Schools in Enugu State for the attainment of productivity and Sustainable Development Goal 4.

Literature Review

Concept of Resources

Resources according to Uche (2020) mean something to turn to, for support or help. Something that can be used to achieve an objective. It is an available supply that can be drawn upon when reached. Resource requires the ability to deal with a situation effectively based on its availability in terms of capital/assets-finance, persons, material, and time. As Wikipedia (2023) puts it, Resource refers to all the materials available in our environment that are technologically accessible, economically feasible, and culturally sustainable and help us to satisfy our needs and wants. Oboloo (2023) opined that resource in business refers to any materials, substances, and services that are used to produce products. Resources can include anything from human labour to raw materials and capital. Resources according to Onukan in Nwile and Adebayo (2022) defined resources as any means by which production and services are provided for the benefit of an organization's clients or the profitability of the organization itself, depending on whether it is profit-oriented or a social service provider. Resources refer to all material items and human elements that are factored into the school business enterprise (Agabi & Akpomi, 2017).

Moreso, resources when appropriately mixed can facilitate teaching and learning. They are essential open tools with which activities and operations of the school are carried out (Sanchez, 2013). According to Enaohwo (1990), resources are seen as the essential tools with which activities and operations of the school are carried. Hence, they cannot be ignored in the economic rationalization of development planning in education.

Time Resources

Maduagwu and Nwogu (2006) opined that school activities are allotted some time frame in which the activities are to be accomplished. Within the school, there is time for morning devotion, time for first and last lessons, break time, mid-term break, holiday, etc. There are also specific lessons allotted to this time. Maduagwu and Nwogu further stated that when these are not properly utilized, school goals are not realized. The other resources, human resources make use of time in the performance of functions. Time is utilized to maintain facilities, delegate functions, or even spend fiscal cash. Armstrong in Maduagwu and Nwogu (2006) proposed that time could be managed through the following: Analyze one's job to establish orders of priority among objectives and between tasks; Analyzing how time is spent on such items relating to your jobs such as reading, writing, telephoning, dealing with people, attending meetings, and class, traveling, etc; Use the diary to free at least one day from any appointment or have some unallotted time for yourself; Plan your work for the week; Organize your daily work by stating what to do in order of priority; Organize other people; your secretary, boss, messenger, and educate them on what to do.

Time resources are crucial to education as they directly impact a student's learning experience, academic experience, academic success, and overall development. Efficient time management allows students to balance their academic workload with extracurricular activities, personal commitments, and social interaction. By effectively utilizing their time, students can develop their time, students can develop proper study habits, allocate sufficient time for studying, and maintain a structured routine. This enables them to absorb information effectively, retain knowledge, and apply it in various academic contexts. Time resources also contribute to the quality of education when students have adequate time to engage in deep learning, critical thinking, and collaborative activities, they can develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter. Time allows for comprehensive exploration of topics, independent research, and meaningful discussion that enhances the learning process.

Sustainable Development Goal 4 and its Significance.

Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) on the other hand is one of the 17 global goals established by the United Nations in 2015 as part of the 2030 agenda for sustainable development. SDG 4 aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all (United Nations, 2022). That is, SDG 4, also known as Sustainable Development Goal 4, is one of the 17 global goals set by the United Nations General Assembly in 2015. the goal aims to ensures inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. The significance of SDG 4 cannot be overstated, as access to quality education is crucial for the development of individuals, community and Nations. Education is a fundamentals human right and a key driver of sustainable development. It empowers individuals, reduces poverty, promotes economic growth, and foster cohesion. However, the attainment of SDG 4 is public secondary schools in Enugu State is faced with numerous challenges one of the major challenges is the inadequate allocation of resources for education. This has fed to a lack of infrastructures, teaching materials, and qualified teachers in many families to afford quality education for their children. This has resulted in low enrolment rate and high dropout rates, particularly among girls and children from low-income families.

Time Resource Availability

Time resource availability refers to the amount of time accessible for educational activities within public secondary schools. It plays a crucial role in determining the quality of instruction and learning outcomes, especially in the pursuit of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4). In Enugu State, factors such as school hours, teacher availability, and student attendance significantly affect time availability. Public schools often face disruptions due to teacher absenteeism, inadequate staffing, or external events like strikes and public holidays, which reduce the effective instructional time. Additionally, administrative tasks and extracurricular activities can further limit the time allocated for core academic subjects. These constraints can lead to incomplete curriculum coverage, affecting students' preparedness for exams and overall learning outcomes. Enhancing time resource availability through better teacher-student ratios, improved scheduling, and minimizing disruptions is essential for aligning the educational system with the goals of SDG 4 in Enugu State.

Time Resource Utilization

Utilization of resources according to Ngurukwem in Olelewe et al (2014) is the proportion of the available time a system is operating in terms of educational resources; it could refer to the extent of available resources that are put to use. It, therefore, becomes imperative that the availability and adequate utilization of educational resources such as human, material, physical, and financial in public secondary schools in Enugu State are explored to determine their applications for knowledge delivery as well as its relationship between resource availability and performance toward achieving Sustainable Development Goal 4 of Sustainable Development Goals. Resource utilization refers to how effectively available time is used to achieve educational goals. In public secondary schools in Enugu State, efficient use of time is crucial for enhancing teaching and learning outcomes, especially in the context of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), which focuses on inclusive and equitable quality education. Effective time utilization ensures that the time allocated for instruction, learning, and extracurricular activities is optimized.

Quality Education for the Attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4

UNICEF as cited in IGI Global, (2024) provides a very comprehensive definition of quality education that includes healthy learners who are well-nourished, are ready to participate and learn, whose learning is supported by their families and communities; healthy, safe, and supportive environments; content that includes the foregoing elements and peace; inclusive child-centered processes that are facilitated by competent self-driven teachers; and actual outcomes that encompass life-supportive knowledge, skills and attitudes, and are linked to national goals for education (equity) and positive participation in society. Particularly critical (for sustainability) is UNICEF's statement that effective and appropriate stimulation in a child's early years influences brain development and is necessary for emotional regulation, arousal, and behavioural management. Ultimately, quality education is not just about acquiring knowledge and skills but also about fostering values, attitudes, and behaviors that contribute to a more just, equitable, and sustainable world. It empowers individuals to fulfill their potential, participate fully in society, and contribute to building a better future for themselves and future generations. Quality education is a fundamental component of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) and is essential for individuals, societies, and economies to thrive

Theoretical Review

Chester Bernard (1938) Efficiency and Effectiveness of Organization Theory. Chester Bernard's 1938 work, "The Functions of the Executive," emphasizes organizational efficiency and effectiveness. Efficiency involves optimizing resource use to minimize waste and maximize productivity, while effectiveness focuses on achieving goals and meeting customer expectations. Bernard argues for a balance between the two, influencing modern management practices to achieve optimal organizational performance. Achievement Goal Theory Propounded by Dweck and Leggett (1988): Achievement Goal Theory, proposed by Weck and Leggett (1988), explains how individuals' motivations and goals in achievement settings influence behavior. It identifies two key goals: mastery (focused on personal growth and learning) and performance (focused on outperforming others). These goals relate to task or ego orientations, with task orientation driven by intrinsic motivation, and ego orientation by extrinsic rewards. Applied to SDG 4, resource availability and utilization impact goal orientations, affecting how individuals pursue educational achievement, either competitively or for personal growth.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised all 293 principals (148 male and 145 female), and the 8,594 teachers, that is, (1803 male and 6,653 female teachers), which gave a total of 8,887 respondents from all public secondary schools in Enugu State. The sample of this study comprised 169 principals and 210 teachers, this gave a total sample of three hundred and seventy-nine (379) respondents. This was ascertained using the Taro Yamane formula. Stratified sampling techniques were used in this study. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled Time Resource Availability and Utilization for the Attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 Questionnaire (TRAUASDGQ) and a 5-item Checklist. The questionnaire was classified into two sections. The 7-item questionnaire was responded to on a four-

point modified Likert scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), and Very Low Extent (VLE). Which seeks to ascertain the extent to which time Resources is adequately allocated in Public Secondary Schools in Enugu State for the attainment of productivity and Sustainable Development Goal 4. The validity of the instrument was established by the researcher’s supervisors and two other experts in the area of Measurement and Evaluation, the University of Port Harcourt. To ascertain the reliability coefficient of the research instrument of this study, Cronbach Alpha statistic was utilized. the instruments were administered to 20 respondents, 10 teachers and 10 principals in public Secondary Schools in Enugu State who share the same characteristics. The overall reliability stood at 0.85 which was considered reliable and adequate for the study. The researcher with some research assistants trained for this purpose, administered the instrument and the instruments were collected on the spot to ascertain accuracy. The research assistants were educated on the location of the selected schools, the method of administration, how to identify a valid response, and collation and analysis of the responses collected using the instrument. Research question 1 raised in the study was answered using Percentage, while research question 2 raised in the study was answered using Mean and Standard Deviation. The Hypothesis was tested by the use of a z-test at a 0.05 level of significance.

DATA ANALYSIS

Research Question one: *To what level are time resources available to impact productivity and attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in Public Secondary Schools in Enugu State?*

Table 1. Percentages of available and not available time resources impact productivity and attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in Public Secondary Schools in Enugu State.

S/N	Items	Available	Not Available	Percentage Available	Percentage Not Available
1	School timetable	378	1	99.73	0.27
2	Attendance book	359	20	94.72	5.28
3	Logbook	372	7	98.15	1.85
4	School academic Calander	377	2	99.48	0.52
5	Teacher’s registration book	376	3	99.20	0.80
Average		372.4	6.6	98.26	1.74

Table 1, shows the figures and percentages of the respondents (teachers) on school timetables, attendance books, log books, School academic calendar and teachers’ registration book on items 1-5 with the following percentages of 99.73, 94.72, 98.15, 99.48 and 99.20 as the current level of time resources available, while 0.27, 5.28, 1.85, 0.52 and 0.80 as the current level of time resources not available to impact productivity and attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in Public Secondary Schools in Enugu State.

Summarily with the average percentage of 98.26 as a percentage available and 1.74 as a percentage not available, it is agreed that time resources are available to a high level to impact productivity and attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in Public Secondary Schools in Enugu State.

Research Question Two: *To what extent are time resources adequately allocated in Public Secondary schools in Enugu State for the attainment of productivity and Sustainable Development Goal 4?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Mean of male and female Teachers on the extent are time resources adequately allocated in Public Secondary schools in Enugu State for the attainment of productivity and Sustainable Development Goal 4

S/No	Items	Male Teachers (N = 186)		Female Teachers (N = 193)		Mean Set (X ₁ X ₂)	Decision
		Mean (X ₁)	SD	Mean (X ₂)	SD		
1	Lessons are well-planned and adhere to the scheduled time frame without unnecessary delays for effective teaching and learning.	2.94	1.01	3.00	1.10	2.97	Great Extent
2	Teachers effectively utilize the allocated class time to cover the curriculum comprehensively.	2.91	0.97	2.99	0.99	2.95	Great Extent
3	Effective assessment practices (conducting assessments and grading students' work) are implemented to achieve sustainable Development Goal 4.	3.95	0.97	3.09	1.15	3.52	Great Extent
4	School timetables are strictly adhered to, ensuring that classes start and end on time.	2.65	1.11	2.96	0.99	2.80	
5	Teachers are available during designated times for student consultations and additional support outside of regular class hours	3.84	1.10	2.83	1.35	3.33	Great Extent
6	Adequate time is allocated for students to complete homework and assignments without overwhelming their schedules	2.97	1.09	3.32	1.02	3.14	Great Extent
7	Extra-curricular activities are appropriately scheduled and managed without disrupting academic learning time	2.97	1.09	3.32	1.02	3.10	Great Extent
8	Sufficient time is allocated for students to prepare for exams with the academic calendar.	3.20	1.11	3.21	1.06	3.20	Great Extent
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		3.17	1.05	3.09	1.08	3.13	Great Extent

According to Table 2, it was revealed that items 1-8 produced mean scores of 2.97, 2.95, 3.59, 2.80, 3.33, 3.14, 3.10 and 3.20 from the responses of the male and female teachers sampled for the study set of items. The criterion mean rule equally applied to these items and as such the items with mean responses above the criterion mean score of 2.50 were agreed upon for both respondents while the items with mean values that were less than the criterion mean score were disagreed. In summary, the grand mean score of 3.17 from the male teachers and 3.09 from the female teachers indicated that the male and female teachers agreed on the items as the extent in which time resources are adequately allocated in Public Secondary schools in Enugu State for the attainment of productivity and Sustainable Development Goal 4.

The highest mean set score of 3.52 implied that on average, effective assessment practices (conducting assessments and grading students' work) are implemented to achieve sustainable Development Goal 4, while the lowest mean set score of 2.80 indicated that the teachers also agreed on average that school timetables are strictly adhered to, ensuring that classes start and end on time. The average mean set score of 3.13 implied that the teachers averagely agreed on the items as the extent are time resources adequately allocated in Public Secondary schools in Enugu State for the attainment of productivity and Sustainable Development Goal 4.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the mean rating scores of Rural teachers and Urban teachers regarding the extent to which financial resources are utilized for the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Table 3: Z-test analysis of the difference between the mean rating scores of Rural teachers and Urban teachers regarding the extent to which financial resources are utilized for the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in public secondary schools in Enugu State

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of Significance	of Decision
Rural	209	3.13	1.11	377	0.95	1.96	0.05	Significant Accept H ₀₁ (z-cal, < z-crit.)
Urban	170	3.02	1.12					

According to Table 3, the z-crit value was 1.96 and the z-cal. value was 0.95. The null hypothesis was accepted because the z-cal. value of 0.95 was less than the z-crit. value of 1.96. This suggests that there is no significant difference in the mean rating scores of Rural and Urban respondents regarding the extent to which financial resources are utilized for the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

The following summaries of findings were highlighted based on the analysis of data collected and presented in the study:

Available time resources to impact productivity and attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4.

The average percentage of 98.26 as a percentage available and 1.74 as a percentage not available, it is therefore agreed that time resources are available for the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in public secondary schools in Enugu State. The responses from the teachers showed that there was a high percentage of the availability of time resources for the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in public secondary schools in Enugu State in all the items (16-20). This is in line with Maduagwu and Nwogu (2006) opined that school activities are allotted some time frame in which the activities are to be accomplished. Within the school, there is time for morning devotion, time for first and last lessons, break time, mid-term break, holiday, etc. There are also specific lessons allotted to this time.

Time resources adequately allocated in Public Secondary schools for the attainment of productivity and Sustainable Development Goal 4

The average mean set score of 3.13 implied that the teachers averagely agreed on the items as the extent are time resources adequately allocated in Public Secondary schools in Enugu State for the attainment of productivity and Sustainable Development Goal 4. The result of the study revealed that the male and female respondents with an average mean of 3.17 and 3.09 respectively, agreed on the extent of time resources adequately allocated in Public Secondary schools in Enugu State for the attainment of productivity and Sustainable Development Goal 4. Similarly, there was no significant difference between the mean rating score of male and female teachers on the extent to which time resources were adequately allocated in Public Secondary schools in Enugu State for the attainment of productivity and Sustainable Development Goal 4. According to Maduagwu and Nwogu (2006), time resources are crucial to education as they directly impact a student’s learning experience, academic experience, academic success, and overall development.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that time resources are partially available in public secondary schools in Enugu State. While the study shows that time resources are generally available, there are still areas where improvements need to be made to ensure their optimal utilization for achieving Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4). The adequate utilization of available time resources is critical for the attainment of SDG 4. The findings suggest that while there are efforts to allocate time effectively, there is still room for improvement in specific areas such as lesson planning, classroom management, and minimizing disruptions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To enhance the availability and utilization of time resources for the attainment of SDG 4 in public secondary schools in Enugu State, the following recommendations are made:

1. Provide teachers with comprehensive training on effective time management techniques, including lesson planning, classroom management, and time allocation strategies.
2. Conduct regular monitoring and evaluation of time resource utilization to identify areas for improvement and implement necessary interventions.

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